

Understanding the Relationship and Bond Between Grandparents and Grandchildren

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ABSTRACT

The connection between both grandparents and grandchildren is extremely crucial. In today's day and age however, there is a large gap between the two due to technology and distance. The present study aims to explore the presence of emotional attachment between grandparents and grandchildren in this era of technology. In order to do this, a survey was created using Google Forms. The data was collected from 14 grandchildren (age range <13 to 23+) and 14 grandparents (n grandmothers = 5, n grandfathers = 9). Statistical analysis such as t-test was carried out in the present study. Findings reveal that there is no significant difference across gender, age, family type among grandparents and their attachment to grandchildren. Furthermore, for grandchildren, findings showed that there is a significant difference in terms of attachment, with more grandchildren feeling closer to their grandfathers. There was no significant difference between medium of interaction (face to face / technology) and frequency of interaction (Daily / Weekly / Monthly / Yearly / None). When grandchildren were asked to share about their connection with their grandparents, a majority of them responded in a positive manner.

Keywords: *Grandparents, Grandchildren, Attachment, Emotional Connection, Technology*

1. INTRODUCTION

The bond between grandparents and grandchildren is shaped by the roles grandparents play, the emotional closeness they share, and their responsibilities in child-rearing, with notable differences between collectivistic and individualistic societies. In the family system, grandparents often provide essential practical and emotional support while in collectivistic societies, where family cohesion is highly valued, grandparents are actively involved in daily child-rearing, maintaining cultural traditions, and supporting family unity. In individualistic societies, where independence is emphasized, grandparents might play a more peripheral role, offering occasional support and engagement (Adcox, "6 Factors of Grandparent-Grandchild Closeness").

Emotional closeness between grandparents and grandchildren varies with cultural context. Collectivistic cultures foster frequent, close-knit interactions, resulting in deep emotional bonds and a strong sense of belonging. In individualistic cultures, interactions may be less frequent but still significant, providing valuable emotional support.

Regarding child-rearing responsibilities, collectivistic cultures often see grandparents as co-caregivers who help impart cultural values and traditions. In individualistic societies, grandparents typically have a supportive role, focusing on occasional care and emotional support rather than daily parenting. Cultural context influences how these roles and relationships are expressed and valued within different family systems(Adcox, "6 Factors of Grandparent-Grandchild Closeness").

Attachment theory, developed by John Bowlby and expanded by Mary Ainsworth, provides a framework for understanding the emotional bonds between grandparents and grandchildren. Bowlby introduced the idea that early emotional bonds, especially between infants and their caregivers, form a secure base that influences later relationships. This theory initially focused on parent-child interactions but has been extended to include grandparent-grandchild relationships, emphasizing how early attachment experiences shape emotional connections throughout life.

Mary Ainsworth's research further refined attachment theory by identifying different attachment styles through her "Strange Situation" experiment (Holmes & Holmes, 2014). She classified attachment into secure, anxious-resistant, and anxious-avoidant styles based on children's responses to separation and reunion with caregivers. These attachment styles are relevant in understanding how grandchildren relate to their grandparents, with secure attachments often leading to stronger, more positive relationships.

Recent studies applying attachment theory to grandparent-grandchild bonds have shown that emotional closeness can reflect secure attachment patterns. For instance, frequent, supportive interactions between grandparents and grandchildren foster emotional security and well-being. Research highlights that a strong emotional bond often mirrors the characteristics of secure attachment, where mutual support and regular communication play crucial roles(Reitzes and Mutran, 2004).

Maintaining these intergenerational bonds involves addressing challenges such as geographic distance, family conflicts, and health issues. Understanding these relationships through

attachment theory underscores the importance of consistent, supportive interactions to sustain emotional closeness. Regular communication and expressions of affection help preserve these valuable connections, reinforcing the emotional security and well-being of both grandparents and grandchildren (Poehlmann, 2003).

The shift from joint family systems to nuclear family structures has impacted the relationship between grandparents and grandchildren by reducing the frequency of face-to-face interactions. In joint families, extended relatives lived together, allowing for regular shared activities like traditional board games and storytelling, which strengthened emotional bonds. With the move to nuclear families, where extended relatives often live separately, maintaining these close connections has become more challenging due to physical distance.

The geographic separation inherent in nuclear family structures can limit the opportunities for regular, meaningful interaction between grandparents and grandchildren. This separation has made it more difficult for families to engage in shared activities and maintain emotional closeness. However, technology has emerged as a crucial tool in addressing this issue, helping to bridge the gap created by physical distance.

Modern technology facilitates ongoing communication between grandparents and grandchildren through video calls, messaging apps, and social media platforms. These tools allow for virtual face-to-face interactions and the sharing of daily experiences, helping to sustain emotional bonds despite the physical separation. Additionally, video games and digital activities provide new ways for grandparents and grandchildren to connect, offering collaborative or competitive play that can enhance their relationship.

In summary, while the shift to nuclear family structures has posed challenges for maintaining close relationships between grandparents and grandchildren, technology has played a vital role in bridging the gap. By enabling regular communication and providing new forms of shared activities, technology helps preserve and strengthen these important familial bonds, adapting to the evolving family dynamics. A research paper by Kornhaber and Woodward, 2005, goes into the impact of the relationship between the two generations. It aimed to show why the relationship is so important. The reason why this paper is so important is because it shows why this relationship is even worth saving. If it is, then it would make sense to continue with the research. The Vital Connection does provide information on why the relationship between grandparents and grandkids are so important by stating how

grandparents give support to grandchildren similar to parental support while grandchildren make grandparents happy. They figured this out through a series of surveys sent to both participants. Questions that were included in this survey asked about how close the two are, how much time they spend together, what they would do when they did spend time together, and more. Additionally, this research paper outlines the Attachments theory and the Family systems theory. The Attachment Theory states that grandparents can act as attachment figures which is crucial for emotional development. Research also shows that this theory highlights the crucial role of caregiver responsiveness in contributing to attachments. It is continued to be researched by adding applications to other diverse cultures. The Family Systems Theory talks about how everyone in the family has a crucial role with grandparents acting as layers of support and guidance to their grandkids. Studies also show that grandparents play a huge part in giving values, showing tradition, culture, and family history. This could help for grandchildren to get a sense of belongingness and identity both culturally and a self-identity. The theory also talks about how one maintains autonomy while being connected to their family. It has also been researched that having arguments with others can impact family dynamics negatively. This theory, however, also over simplifies the family dynamic.

The research aimed to see how big of an impact age has on memory. When aging, how much does the memory change? Does it get better, worsen, or stay the same? To achieve this, the research paper used a meta-analysis approach which is essentially using multiple research papers to do their research and see what is common in between them. The reason why this research paper is valuable is due to the fact that a stronger memory helps in the game of lambs and tigers as well as remembering things about the grandchildren. Through looking at research at taking out papers that were not reliable and did not have references, the author of the research paper came to the conclusion that older people tend to be worse in content memory but better in context memory. Both of these two types of memories come from the Dual-Processes theory which states there are two main types of theories. Context theory is details and circumstances while content theory is pure facts. Additionally, the author of this research paper talked about the Age and Memory theory. The theory states that age leads to neural change but it can be slowed down through cognitive training so that the mind stays sharp (Spencer & Raz, 1995).

One more research paper found this time talked about the grandchildren instead of grandparents (Ruzic-Baf et al., 2015). This research paper aimed to find out the impact of videogames on young people. It is important to take a look at this research paper as it

provides an insight to why the younger generation could be inclined to play more videogames. The author of this research paper used three modes to collect data. First they conducted surveys about gaming habits. They also performed controlled experiments to see how video games affect aggression and violence. Lastly they tracked people over time to see how video games affect one's mood. They then used both quantitative and qualitative analysis to both identify patterns and get an in-depth insight into personal experiences. Through this, they came to the conclusion that if moderated, gaming actually benefits the kid, teaching them valuable things like teamwork and spatial awareness. Although, too much gaming can lead to a risk on one's health and social aspects. There were two theories covered in this research paper being Uses and Gratifications Theory and Social Cognitive Theory. The Uses and Gratifications Theory states the reason why people use social media and play video games is to satisfy needs like social interaction and entertainment. It emphasizes the purposeful media use as well as that different media are chosen by the different gratifications they provide. This theory however does not take into structural differences. Social Cognitive Theory states that young people might learn behaviors shown in video games both good or bad. Some studies also showed that video games can enhance cognitive thinking, spatial awareness, and multitasking abilities. This theory supports and emphasizes learning through observational learning as it highlights self-efficacy behaviors. Despite this, the theory is often said to be oversimplifying a more complex behavior. Although, it has been shown in the past that excessive gaming can lead to many mental health concerns like depression and anxiety.

This research paper aimed to detect the different reaction times between the two different age groups. Since both older and younger generations would be playing this game, it would be helpful to know which would have a better reaction time and how it would affect the gameplay. The methodology for this research paper used an age group of 18-30 and with an older group from ages 60+. They also made sure the sample size was enough to account for many outliers. Both groups are asked to do a single detection task on a computer screen. The main thing they look for in these tasks are reaction times and accuracy. They are all seated comfortably and the environment they are put in is the same. To examine the difference, they used t-tests or ANOVA. Through this, they confirmed that older people do tend to have a slower reaction time than the younger generations as the younger group were more accurate with the task given. Some theories stated in this research paper include the General Slowing Hypothesis which is basically saying that aging causes a decline in all cognitive functions due to the central nervous system. The correlation of structural and functional neural changes includes a decrease in brain metabolism and reduced synaptic

density(essential indicator of development).Additionally is the Processing Speed Theory which states the reason for a slower reaction time is that the speed of your brain processing something decreases as you get older, in turn increasing the reaction time. Due to changes like the reduced synaptic density and the decrease in cerebral blood flow, there is a decline in cognitive function. This theory also states that daily activities that enhance the processing speed could lower the negative effects. The last theory mentioned was the Sensory Decline theory which states that sensory organs getting weaker such as the eyes and ears, results in the reaction time increasing. It also shows that there is an increased cognitive load, and social isolation from sensory decline. One other study on this was that slower reaction times lead to slower motor skills and that older people have a slower reaction time when compared to younger people. Some factors to this include older people getting distracted more, slower motor responses, and that most older people don't do much high cognitive activities due to retirement. The research paper also states how this could affect driving, help in work, something design wise to support older people(Klasnja et al., 2022).

2. METHODOLOGY:

2.1 Aim :

The present study aims to understand the attachment and emotional bond between grandparents and grandchildren.

2.2 Objectives:

1. To investigate the role of family type on grandparent - grandchildren attachment
2. To investigate the role of gender on grandparent - grandchildren attachment
3. To investigate the role of Age on grandparent - grandchildren attachment
4. To investigate the role of Technology on grandparent - grandchildren attachment

2.3 Sample and sampling technique

In the present study the data was collected from grandparents(n = 14) and grandchildren(n = 14). The age range for the grandparents was 39 and below to 70+ and for the grandchildren it was 13 and below to 23+. Purposive sampling technique was used to procure data from the respondents.

2.4 Research design

A quantitative research design was employed wherein two google forms were created. The survey form for the grandparents consisted of 26 items. The survey form for the

grandchildren consisted of 24 items.

Instrumentation

1. **Grandparents Survey** - The survey contains 16 items measuring the attachment and bond perceived by grandchildren towards grandparents. The responses are on a scale ranging from Always to Never as well as Very Much to No.
2. **Grandchildren Survey** - The survey contains 15 items measuring the attachment and bond perceived by grandchildren towards grandparents. The responses are on a scale ranging from Always to Never.

3. RESULTS:

Figure 1: The mean total score across gender for grandparents (M Female = 38.6, M Male = 36.78)

Table 1 shows the t-test for gender and the total score of grandparents on emotional attachment

		N	M	SD	t	p	Cohen's d
Total Score	Male	9	36.78	8.24	-0.43	0.677	0.24
	Female	5	38.6	6.27			

The findings on *Table 1* show that there is no significant mean difference on the total score with $t = -0.43$ and $p = 0.677(p > 0.05)$. The Cohen's d value of 0.24 reveals a small effect size.

Figure 2: The mean total score across family types for grandparents(M Nuclear = 39.25, M Joint = 35)

Table 2 shows the t-test for family type and the total score of grandparents on emotional attachment

		N	M	SD	t	p	Cohen's d
Total Score	Nuclear Family	8	39.25	3.77	1.07	.306	0.58
	Joint Family	6	35	10.49			

The findings on *Table 2* show that there is no significant mean difference on the total score of grandparents across family-type with $t = 1.07$ and $p = 0.306$ ($p > 0.05$). The Cohen's d value of 0.58 reveals a moderate effect size.

Figure 3: The mean total score of Age of grandparenthood (M 46-55= 39.22, M 56-65= 31.5).

Table 3 shows the t-test for age of grandparenthood and total score on emotional attachment

		N	M	SD	t	p	Cohen's d
Total Score	46-55	9	39.22	4.24	-1.94	.079	1.16
	56-65	4	31.5	10.66			

The findings on Table 3 reveal that there is no significant mean difference on the total score of grandparents on emotional attachment and the age of grandparenthood, with $t = -1.94$ and $p = 0.079$ ($p > 0.05$). The Cohen's d value of 1.16 represents a large effect size.

Figure 4: The mean total score across gender for grandchildren (M Female = 38, M Male = 33.33)

Table 4 shows the t-test for gender and the total score of grandchildren on emotional attachment

		N	M	SD	t	p	Cohen's d
Total Score	Male	8	38	6.59	-1.24	.24	0.67
	Female	6	33.33	7.53			

The findings on Table 4 show that there is no significant mean difference on the total score with $t = -1.24$ and $p = 0.24$ ($p > 0.05$). The Cohen's d value of 0.67 reveals a moderate effect size.

Figure 5: The mean total score across who grandchildren feel closer to (M Both = 39.29, M Grandfather = 35.8, M Neither = 25)

Table 5 shows the ANOVA test for who grandchildren feel closer too and the total score for grandchildren on emotional attachment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2
Closest Bond With	317.77	2	158.89	5.08	.027	0.48
Residual	344.23	11	31.29			
Total	662	13				

The findings on Table 5 show that there is a significant mean difference on the total score with $p = 0.027(p < 0.05)$. The η^2 value of 0.48 reveals a small effect size.

Figure 6: The mean total score across the frequency of interactions between grandchildren and grandparents (M Monthly = 42, M Daily = 38.33, M Weekly =38.2, M Year = 30.33, M Not at all = 23)

Table 6 shows the Anova test across the frequency of interactions between grandchildren and grandparents and the total score for grandchildren on emotional attachment

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	p	η^2
Frequency of interaction	195.87	3	65.29	2.07	.175	0.41
Residual	284.13	9	31.57			
Total	480	12				

The findings on Table 6 show that there is no significant mean difference on the total score with $p = 0.175(p > 0.05)$. The η^2 value of 0.41 reveals a small effect size. The frequencies of interaction taken into consideration were daily, weekly, monthly, and yearly. "Not at all" was removed due to less responses.

Figure 7: The mean total score across the medium of interaction (M Technology = 11, M Meeting them in person = 3)

Table 7 shows the t-test for the medium of interaction and the total score of grandchildren on emotional attachment

		t	df	p	Cohen's d
Total Score	Equal variances	-0.61	11	.556	0.4
	Unequal variances	-0.87	7.42	.411	0.57

The findings on Table 7 show that there is no significant mean difference on the total score with $t = -0.61$ and $p = 0.556$ ($p > 0.05$). The Cohen's d value of 0.4 reveals a small effect size. The survey included open-ended questions wherein the grandchildren were asked to explain the connection they share with their grandparents. Out of the total respondents (N=14), 85.7% of respondents reported positive connections which can be explained by statements such as “my grandparents are the only two people that make me happy in the whole wide world” . Whereas 21.4% of respondents reported negative connections which can be seen through statements such as “I am not as close to them because they live in India and I am only able to visit every few years, and I am not that good at speaking Telugu.”

4. DISCUSSION

Findings in the present study reveal no significant difference between grandparents living in joint and nuclear family type with regards to their attachment with grandchildren. Previous research has commonly looked at family types' impact on grandchildren's attachment rather than that of grandparents. However, Ramchandra and Salunkhe (2014) found that for the elderly the family type significantly impacted their health. With growing age, more support is needed from family, old people fare better in joint families compared to nuclear families. Furthermore, research has suggested that nuclear families create loneliness among the elderly, particularly, females (K & S, 2018).

Furthermore, it is also found that there is a significant difference with different ages of grandparenthood with regards to their attachment with grandchildren. Older grandparents tend to be more affectionate but also tend to contact and spend time with grandchildren less than younger grandparents (Silverstein & Long, 1998). Additionally, younger grandparents tend to feel older than those who are around the same age but not grandparents. However, this can be reversed later on if they have to give grandchild care (Bordone & Arpino, 2016).

When comparing the gender of grandparents and how it relates to their attachment with grandchildren, however, previous studies showed a multitude of answers. A study on 33 grandmothers and 33 grandfathers revealed the perception of grandparenthood for grandfathers is very different than that for grandmothers (Silverstein & Long, 1998). Some studies show that maternal grandmothers tend to be closer to grandchildren but this can change greatly as time goes on and the grandchildren get older. (Mann et al., 2013).

When looking at who grandchildren feel closer to, studies show that despite grandchildren being closer to grandmothers, this can vary from age and gender. In particular, older grandsons bond more with their grandfathers (Mann et al., 2013). Parental grandmothers, on the other hand, benefit from affection as they are more associated with affection and closeness (Bernhold & Giles, 2019). The data collected in the surveys showed no one being closer to just their grandmother, proving how there are many factors that can change how close one is with their grandparents.

Additionally, research indicates that there are many mediums of interactions between grandparents and grandchildren but the most common is face-to-face interactions despite other methods gaining popularity (Quadrello et al., 2005). In part, a difference between face-to-face interactions and technology could be immigration. On top of that, younger grandparents tend to meet with grandchildren more often while older grandparents tend to provide more financial support (Silverstein & Marengo, 2001).

The frequency of interaction between grandparents and grandchildren was also studied in the present research wherein findings revealed that most interactions occurred monthly ($M= 42$) and the medium of interaction most commonly adopted was technology. This could be attributed to the geographical distance between families in the present times wherein technology such as Skype, FaceTime etc. emerge as a great aid in helping people stay connected despite living apart.

5. CONCLUSION

To conclude, grandparents and grandchildren share an emotional bond that cannot be triumphed by any other. Grandparents care for grandchildren by providing them both emotional and physical support. Despite this, there is a large generational gap due to technology.

In the present study findings had revealed the effect of family type, age, gender upon the attachment between grandparents and grandchildren. The role of technology was also researched upon.

This study is not devoid of its limitations. Firstly, the sample size under consideration is small, hence it is not a good representative of the population under study. Secondly, a more intergenerational approach within the family structure can provide better understanding of the attachment. Additionally, most of the people who filled out a survey were from Asian descent, which may not show the full few. Instead, getting a wide array of ethnicities and races would provide for a more holistic set of data.

Future implications:

It is crucial to study the bond between gc and gp as in the formative years the role played by gp particularly in the Indian social context is paramount. The study can be done on a larger sample size, and can consider cross cultural comparisons when looking into gp and gc attachment. This will aid researchers and families in developing a better understanding of the emotional bond and it will provide them with recommendations to make the bond stronger as due to the geographical distance the attachment can eventually grow weaker. This will aid researchers and families in developing a better understanding of the emotional bond and it will provide them with recommendations to make the bond stronger as due to the geographical distance the attachment can eventually grow weaker.

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